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Self-Emptying Love in Compassionate Service - In Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity

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Abstract

Despite the differences between Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity, there is a possibility for transcending them and finding a common ground of experiencing the core of both religions as a self-emptying process of attaining the consciousness of Jesus or the Buddha and fulfilling one's call to self-emptying love in compassionate service to all beings. Such a process is made possible through an inter-religious learning experience. In this case, Vipassana meditation becomes an effective vehicle for continuing that learning process.

Introduction

Buddhism and Christianity are two of the world's most significant religions, with different origins, teachings, and practices. While they share some similarities, they differ fundamentally, including their beliefs about the nature of existence, the purpose of life, and the role of the divine. Since there are many different sects within Buddhism and Christianity, I have taken Mahayana Buddhism and Catholicism as representatives of the two religions. Mahayana Buddhism is a branch of Buddhism that emerged in India and spread throughout Asia, including China, Japan, and Korea. Catholicism is a branch of Christianity that has its roots in the Middle East and has spread worldwide. Both sects claim to have

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kept their teaching closest to the original teachings of the founders of their respective religions.

Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity, while based on the teachings of Siddhartha Gautama and Jesus Christ, respectively, have distinct beliefs and practices. Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity differ significantly in their approach to salvation, the role of clergy, values, funeral rituals, and view of reality. Mahayana aims for Buddhahood, liberation from suffering, through personal enlightenment, with no centralized authority or hierarchy. It values compassion, wisdom, and altruism, and follows the Bodhisattva path. Funeral rituals often involve cremation and chanting of prayers, with belief in reincarnation. Emptiness, the concept that all phenomena lack inherent existence, is central to its view of reality.

On the other hand, Catholicism believes in salvation through faith in Jesus Christ and good works, with a hierarchical structure led by the Pope. It values love, faith, service to others, and charity. Funeral rituals often involve a church service, procession to the cemetery, and burial, with a belief in resurrection. The existence of a personal God who created the universe and actively intervened in the world is essential to its view of reality. Despite these differences, both religions emphasize compassion and ethical behaviour and believe in helping others.

Whatever may be the similarities and differences between Buddhism and Christianity in general or Mahayana Buddhism and Catholicism in particular, the Buddha reminds us of Jesus in his attitude towards renunciation and self-emptying love. Both Buddha and Jesus showed us unique paths towards the cessation of suffering without denying it. Self-emptying love is generated through suffering in one's own bodily existence. In Buddhism, the path that leads to the cessation of suffering is not one of speculation but of praxis by avoiding all kinds of extremes in thought, word, and action. Though Buddhism is depicted as nihilistic and 'anatmic', it must be mentioned simultaneously that it was neither

‘eternalistic’ (Panikkar 1989). Bracketing a Catholic practitioner’s own spiritual world as a journey of sinful souls and saints, is it possible to enter into an experience of the spiritual resources available to a Buddhist practitioner?

1.1. Transcending the differences between both Mahayana Buddhism and Catholicism: A Personal Journey to Find the Common Ground through *Vipassana*

From my experience of doing Vipassana, a Mahayana form of Buddhist meditation, I can say that some mutual fecundation of both religions happens only when one enters into some practice. Beyond intellectual analysis, a certain experience of exploring the inner experience hidden in the practice of a religion can connect one with its spiritual resources as a learning process. “Learning is a relatively permanent behaviour change acquired through a process of reflection based on one’s experience” is a definition I used to hear regularly from our lecturer in Human Behaviour Class during my MSW studies. I never asked the teacher for the reference for the definition but considered it the most appealing one. The change orientation mentioned in the definition inspired me to use it in this paper.

The model of inter-religious learning suggested by Rotting incorporates two aspects of the internal movement of the learner as described by Cobb (1998), namely passing over and coming back: “During this process, we develop a new relation to the other religion and our own. In realizing this new relation as a change we acknowledge that learning has been successful” (Rotting 2007:280).

I had the concrete experience of personally visiting the Vipassana Centre at Igatpuri and doing two 10-day *Vipassana* Meditations in a span of ten years. In my personal journey of discovering the wealth of Buddhism from the background of a Jesuit seeking to understand effective meditation practices, I experienced a certain coalescence of philosophical search and

spiritual search during the practice of *Vipassana*. The philosophical understanding of *sunyata* had already captivated me as I was trying to make a textual study of *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā* of Nagarjuna. A reflection in that context made me realize how the *sunyata* of Buddha and the *kenosis* of Jesus overlapped not just at the conceptual level but also at a deep, experiential level. The significant moments in my life that afforded me such an experience of *sunyata*, however limited it may be, are the experiences connected to my Long Retreat in the novitiate and the 10-day *Vipassana* meditation at Igatpuri, Maharashtra, India. There was a gap of about 10 years between these two programmes. Still, it seemed that the latter was taking me to a “Contemplation to Attain Love,” the last contemplation in the Spiritual Exercises in a natural way without reference to the former, and that too without any reference to the Bible or the Spiritual Exercises. When I take a deep breath and recollect, I still feel both experiences happened in the same spiritual space shared with many other nameless, unknown spiritual seekers. In Rotting’s phrase, both the philosophical terms of *sunyata* and *kenosis* and the spiritual or existential experience of the Long Retreat and the 10-Day *Vipassana* Meditation are “the primal points of contact” for me as I reflect on my inter-religious learning of Buddhism as a Catholic religious, a Jesuit.

Vippasana was an experience of passing to Buddhism from my comfort zone in a Catholic spiritual setting. From a synchronous point of view, now I see both my Christian experience of silence and meditations and that of *Vipassana* taking me to the same process of ridding myself of various inordinate attachments and mental and physical defilements. This process led me to rid myself of many absolutist positions regarding the use of various symbols and even sacraments. During *Vipassana*, when sitting for 10 hours every day was an ordeal. When tears rolled down my cheeks due to the severe pain I used to have on one of my knees when the instructor gently prodded me not to keep my leg out-stretched as I struggled to squat during my meditation, I felt like crying out for help from Jesus as I used to do in my childhood. Then I understood

that that cry for help to Jesus, however spiritual it may be depicted, is a resistance within me to accept the suffering that is involved in disciplining myself, in purifying myself. Self-emptying is a nameless process and part of the spiritual process whatever spiritual tradition I take up. Though imperfectly, I understood what Rotting said: “As a part of the process of religious learning, inter-religious learning influences, changes, and develops one’s faith” (2007:282).

Now I realize my exposure to Vipassana meditation, or rather Mahayana Buddhism, touched the four areas of learning as explained by Rotting: “identity, the act of faith, worldview, and ethic” (2007, p. 282). Now I wish I could learn more to be a Buddhist Christian Jesuit; to be more non-violent, selfless, just, and peace-oriented in all that I do as an expression of my faith in Jesus and the teachings of Buddha; to be more this-worldly without neglecting the concerns of the other world, being present to myself and to the world around me in a compassionate manner; to be more sensitive to the need of interpreting moral codes without being absolutist about anything, as unchangeable.

The different stages mentioned by Rotting (2007:282-283) have been experienced by me in an iterative manner right after my novitiate when I started wondering how the Buddha got that bewitching smile on his face. After entering the world of Buddhism through occasional readings and the intense study of Nagarjuna’s *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā*, I still consider *Vipassana* as an intensive form of dialogue and at the heart of heart, though Buddhism does not acknowledge a personal God, I consider Jesus as “re-presenting” for me what it means to be the Buddha, the Enlightened One, in a synchronous sense, today, here and now, in my struggles and the struggles of suffering humanity. My desire to experience celibacy as a flow of self-emptying love without the slightest obstruction is an ongoing exploration with the occasional discovery of personal insights about my own sexuality and an ongoing creative surrender of myself on the Way of the Cross. Now, as part of “coming back into my own tradition, as a kind of “double

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networking points of contact” I keep referring to “*sunyata-kenosis*”, “*Pratityasamutpada*-communion of saints and natural beings as exemplified in the life of Francis of Assisi”, “*Jeevanmukta*-saints”, and “*nirvana*-“heaven-on-earth”.

John 12:24 became an anchoring verse for me to re-link *sunyata* with the self-emptying required of any disciple of Jesus. Though limited, a few of my Christian friends have shared how the experience of *Vipassana* transformed their philosophical and spiritual outlook on life. During this last Lenten time, as I was reflecting on the *athitthana* of Buddha (sitting posture before his final enlightenment) under the peepul tree that was destined to be the bodhi tree, I was fascinated by the possible comparison with Jesus on the cross as the tree of life. The way Jesus took his suffering liberated humanity as a form of ultimate surrender. Even at that moment, he could have come out of the tree as fictitiously presented by Kazantzakis in his “Last Temptation”. The final victory was won because of the *adhithhana* of Jesus; he was determined to go through the suffering to make me free! Now, I am gently invited to go through a process of transformation within me so that I take up suffering out of love for others out of compassion! Whatever I suffer out of love, becomes an instrument for the well-being of others; ultimately, well-being is salvation here on earth. As I evaluate my Catholic faith, I acknowledge a few areas of growth, especially in matters concerning sins, confession, attitude to non-human creatures in the environment, attitude to the opposite sex, sexuality, and aggression. Many such irrational drives and aspects of human life can be dealt with more harmoniously through silence and contemplation in the *Vipassana* way. Too much absolutist insistence on sacraments may not be justifiable. This I consider as the intra-religious dialogue that goes on within me and I sense something unique happening in my reflections including homilies and interventions such as counselling of people to deal with their sexual struggles.

Going for *vipassana* meditation instead of an annual retreat among the Jesuits has become a kind of “new rooting in one’s own tradition”. I think it was so providential that I went for *vipassana* meditation two times to Igatpuri where I sat with hundreds of other seekers and experienced the beauty and richness of ‘inter-religious learning’ as proposed by Rotting in his article, “Christian Process and Buddhist Reference?” (Rotting 2007). So far, I have been sharing how inter-religious learning has been happening in my life through my exposure to Vipassana, a meditation practice that follows Mahayana Buddhism. But it is enlightening to see how transformation can take place in both Buddhists and Christians: (1) through a process of inculturation as in the case of “bowing” for a “sign of peace” during the eucharistic celebration instead of shaking hands as in Europe; (2) through a process of “transculturation” of their views and practice of faith as in the use of various symbols and props such as bells used in their prayer settings; (3) through a process of concretizing their love through charitable activities in the case of Buddhists and (4) through a process of affirming the dynamic awareness of the presence of God here and now (Rotting 2007:286). The use of symbols as a process of transculturation is worth highlighting. For example, I keep a wooden carved Buddha head in my study cum prayer room. The very sight of this Buddha reminds me of the *adhitthana paramita* of the Buddha, namely determination, resolution, or fixedness of purpose (Anonymous 2023). This quality helped the Buddha attain enlightenment under the Bodhi tree since he resolved that he would not move from his seated posture unless he received enlightenment. This personal experience of mine shows how human beings shape their living environment to support prayer on a small scale. In fact, symbols such as a cross, rosary, or the head of the Buddha, and other reminders of prayer help us become aware of our innermost need to connect to the divine or the transcendent power.

As shared earlier, from an analytical point of view, though many differences could be found between Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity, an attempt at inter-religious learning

shows how a seeker can access the richness of “marrying two religions”. The experience of touching the core of both Mahayana Buddhism and Catholic Christianity lets the seekers from both sects understand the mysterious, dialogical unity of religions. Buddhism can be seen as a protest against the Brahmanical system of ancient India, which blocked individual freedom and social inclusion. Buddhism offered a new way of life, making caste or social status irrelevant in pursuing spiritual liberation by emphasizing personal responsibility and inner transformation rather than external rituals and sacrifices. Though as per their original inspiration, in their attitude to non-violence, meditation, renunciation, and rejection of the caste system, both Buddhism and Christianity should have evinced convergence, we see extreme violence based on ethnic identity, race, and class due to their politicization. At a time when the politicization of religion and dividing people in the name of religion for electoral or capitalist gains has become the order of the day, inter-religious learning is a way forward toward achieving peace, harmony, and social justice among followers of different religions.

2. From ‘my religion as the best religion’ to ‘my religion as one among the many’

In the pluri-religious context of India, every true seeker of inter-religious learning journeys from a position of ‘my religion as the best religion’ to ‘my religion as one among many but a unique path to understanding other religions’. Such seekers realize the following insights regarding religions, inter-religious learning, and practical implications of religion on social justice, peace, and harmony:

- To be religious is part of being human. Religion is a human good. It is born out of a need for transcendence (Moschella, 2017). Religion is part of humans’ need to communicate with nature and all other beings with due regard for their mystery dimension (OpenStax, n.d.). In their search for their own identity as human

beings, they found how inadequate they were to fulfill themselves. They always lacked the power to deal with their own sufferings, especially in the face of their imminent death and destruction (Hewstone and Stroebe, 2020).

- In human beings' search for securing a harmonious life, they have had recourse to systems such as dharma (Das, 2023) or the Decalogue (Kass, 2013). Such systems provide worldviews that sustain socio-cultural foundations that support moral conduct. The principles of moral conduct contained in dharma or the Decalogue are considered given by a superior power, assuring compliance to ensure harmonious societal interactions, particularly in contentious situations.
- In a sense, religion is a universal need but is experienced in unique ways depending on each religion's socio-geographic and cultural context. Sometimes rituals and deities can look extremely grotesque and bizarre, but a proper understanding of these aspects as an evolved reality with its own significance for those who practice it will help us to respect other people's religions.
- The epistemological stand we take to define religion has consequences for understanding religions and their practices. Defining religion could be done in two senses: 1) referring to clear-cut definitions with specific reference to religious studies and academic disciplines, which may not lead to any commonly agreed understanding of it, and 2) explaining the day-to-day understanding of it, which could lead to some consensus (Bergunder, 2014).
- The idea of religion as a culture indicates many subjective and objective aspects of it as a way of life and view of life, taking 'culture' as a broader concept within which many sub-cultures of religions flourish (Unacademy, n.d.). In this existential sense, Indian culture affects every religion practised in India. In that sense, even Christianity has an Indian influence because of its centuries-long dialogue of life with other religions, such as Hinduism and Buddhism, for example, through the common vehicle of Indian culture. The insistence on 'truth' and 'non-

violence' are two important values that we see in all Indian religions. Gandhiji used these pan-Indian values to organize a non-violent resistance movement against the British Empire and brought together even Muslims who did not essentially believe in non-violence as part of their explicit religious practice (Gandhi, 1968).

- Religion as truth indicates two positions: 1) an absolutist position of any religion that tells that it possesses the full truth and only if humans accept that truth and practice that religion as per its rules and rituals will they attain perfection and happiness and 2) a relativist position that every individual or group can have the unique experience of their religious truth and that experience need not be accepted or acknowledged by others.
- When religion is seen as truth, each religion sees itself as the only path to truth. Religious truth thus becomes absolute. This tendency is more common among Semitic religions. The truth seems to be laid down in their Books and some of those who follow such religions swear by their books. They set out to disprove each other, eventually leading to disharmony and even war. "There is no nonviolent way to resolve conflicts when each side believes itself to be in possession of the truth" (Panikkar, 1989: p. xxv). An enlightened view of religion will focus on the fruits of religious practices rather than dogmatic positions.
- Every religion worth the name values truth, service, and moral living. Some have the ideal of promoting selfless service. Through the common search and sharing, people who believe in different religions are likely to value each religion's core values and explore ways and means of accessing their core to unite people to fight against poverty and injustices and attain peace and harmony for all.
- Rotting's view of religion in terms of a cultural perspective has been refreshing, especially when it comes to inter-religious learning (2007). The perspective from the outside makes people think of other religions, especially in the context of the apologetic purpose of Christian missionaries, for instance. Christian

missionaries confronted by other forms of religion began to look for similarities and differences. In fact, there is a growing recognition of the fact that religion is more of a cultural form that has evolved through centuries than anything else (Rotting, 2007).

- In the context of caste-based vulnerabilities, some groups of people who belonged to Hindu cults converted to Christianity with a view to getting better inclusion in society. Though they have improved their socioeconomic status, they do not seem to have improved their socio-cultural identity. Even after conversion, in the grand scheme of caste-based Indian society, the so-called low-caste people still remain low-caste within their own societies. Thus, low-caste Christians are on the lookout for better education to climb the socio-cultural ladder, though the question of inclusion could still be elusive, especially for those who bear the stigma of the so-called low-caste identity such as the Mukkuva Christians of Thiruvananthapuram district, for example (Chiramel, 2014).
- In a sense, Hinduism could be seen as a culture that promotes the caste system, a stratification of society based on birth. This culture permeates every religion in India despite their claim to have more equality based on the teachings of their founders, such as Jesus and Prophet Mohammad. In that sense, we could say that Indian Catholic Christianity is another religion, though it may be subsumed under Catholicism considering the hierarchical churches' allegiance to the Pope in Rome. Thus, we see more heterogeneity than homogeneity when we probe the similarities and differences in different religions. Revisiting Buddhism to rediscover its foundational inspiration to reform the caste-ridden society is an important step for the practitioners of all religions in India. The practice of Buddhist meditation methods such as Vipassana is an inviting step for all, especially when the politicization of religion is burning bridges rather than building them.

Conclusion

The story of a Buddhist monk crossing a river on a makeshift raft can hold symbolic meaning for all followers of religions. For instance, the image of a river can represent the journey of life and the challenges and obstacles that one must face along the way (O'Brien, 2023). It is only through diligent efforts that a person attains spiritual growth. But as one progresses in spiritual life, whatever has been useful to 'cross' some rivers may no longer be relevant for future struggles. Similarly, the image of a makeshift raft can represent the impermanence and imperfection of all things in life, including one's own efforts to achieve spiritual growth. In Christian tradition, the rite of confirmation is a sacrament that represents a deepening of one's faith and commitment to the Christian community. Constructing a makeshift raft and crossing the river with skill and resourcefulness may be a parallel to the effort required to deepen one's faith and commitment to the Christian community. Despite the differences I see in other religions, such a process of transformation is required of every human person, and it is available to all through different rituals as they deepen their commitment to their community through their specific vocation. There is a growing awareness of various global crises that have local manifestations, such as increasing communal and religious riots in the wake of depleting resources, increasing threats to the sustainability of the globe in the context of environmental degradation and global warming, ever-growing fear and anxiety of an imminent nuclear war in the context of the conflict between Russia and Ukraine and the collective despair and hopelessness expressed by international bodies such as United Nations in the context of the lawless confrontation between Hamas and Israel that has led to a horrendous genocide of Palestinian people. In the light of such collective failures of humanity, dialogue that promotes inter-religious learning seems to be an essential way towards reconciling differences or instead recognizing the more profound unity of humanity despite all kinds of contradictions,

including disagreements among religions in terms of their dogmas and praxis.

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